

An insight into Central Bank Digital Currency

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Abstract

The digital payments landscape has evolved in recent years, and the intensity of research into central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) has massively increased. This paper outlines the likely impacts of a CBDC on the economy, with a focus on financial stability and the banking system. It also gives an insight into the design choices and the extent to which they satisfy crucial central bank policy goals. It is intended to be read primarily by those associated with implementing a CBDC, namely policymakers and central banks. A well-designed retail CBDC could benefit the economy by improving payment efficiency and satisfying policy goals such as financial inclusion. It could also protect monetary sovereignty against the recent surge of currency competition, chiefly from cryptocurrencies and stablecoins. The principal risk associated with a CBDC is the potential to cause bank disintermediation and financial instability. The level of disintermediation that a CBDC would cause largely depends on the design choices, which significantly influence the economic impact of the digital currency and how widely it is used by the general public.

Non-Technical Summary

In recent years, the intensity of research into central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) has massively increased. Central bank digital currency is a digital representation of the sovereign currency produced by a centralised monetary authority such as a central bank. This paper focuses on the design choices and likely impact surrounding retail CBDC, the form of CBDC which would have the most substantial impact on the financial system. A retail CBDC is the primary form of this digital currency that most policymakers are considering implementing worldwide.

Introducing a retail CBDC may improve many factors, including financial stability, monetary policy implementation, financial inclusion, domestic and cross-border payments efficiency, and payments safety and robustness. The primary reason for introducing a CBDC varies across different countries, many of which want to provide an alternative form of widely available central bank money in economies where the use of cash is dwindling.

Many central banks also fear the rise of cryptocurrencies and stablecoins, which provide cash alternatives and could compromise the ubiquity of public money, reducing monetary sovereignty. An established retail CBDC is widely considered a disrupting force against the recent explosion in cryptocurrency growth. It would be backed by central bank reserves and could help to cement central banks' monetary sovereignty.

The design choices for CBDC determine its likely impact on the financial system. CBDC must be designed as an attractive form of payment to ensure that it is accepted and used within the economy. However, many fear that CBDC could substitute commercial bank deposits on a large scale and cause disintermediation of the banking sector. This would depend on the design of the operating model; the central bank would have total control over the entire process under a single-tiered CBDC, whereas an intermediated CBDC would involve outsourcing some tasks to financial intermediaries. These intermediaries would include commercial banks and non-bank financial institutions and would likely obtain revenue by charging payment fees. From these fees, commercial banks would be able to retain most of their earnings even if they face a drop in traditional bank deposits. However, the amount of revenue commercial banks and other intermediaries would be allowed to earn largely depends on the extent to which bank disintermediation would cause severe financial instability. There is a growing consideration that commercial banks are no longer 'too big to fail' in the UK, for example, meaning the central bank would not be responsible for keeping them afloat and could allow bank disintermediation to occur.

Another crucial design choice that central banks must make is to introduce a remunerated or non-interest-bearing CBDC. A remunerated CBDC would improve monetary policy transmission and could be increased or lowered to improve or reduce its attractiveness to the general public. A remunerated CBDC also gives central banks the opportunity to implement negative interest rates, eliminating the liquidity trap.

Central banks must also decide which type of ledger system to run CBDC on. A centralised ledger system would involve opening an account directly with the central bank (or with an intermediary) and would facilitate more, quicker transactions than alternatives. The other option is to use distributed ledger technology (DLT), for example, blockchain, which is the underlying system for Bitcoin. Although this system is decentralised and difficult to hack, it is very energy-intensive and faces issues such as slow transaction speeds.

There is somewhat of a trade-off between privacy and security in designing a CBDC. The network must comply with AML, CFT and KYC regulations, requiring financial institutions to verify the identity of their users. However, much of the general public value transactional anonymity, as offered by cash. Central

banks must also decide whether to collect (or allow intermediaries to collect) transaction data or allow transactional privacy.

Some countries have already implemented CBDCs, and many others have introduced, or are planning to introduce, pilot schemes. Other international projects, such as the mCBDC Bridge project, aim to facilitate and speed up cross-border transactions, a key element of CBDC. Central banks worldwide must cooperate on CBDC design to ensure interoperability on issues including cross-border payments. If not, dollarisation could occur, or private currencies could become prevalent and threaten monetary sovereignty worldwide.

Policymakers must be aware of the likely impact of each design choice and ensure that CBDC promotes innovation within the payments sphere. They must also be flexible in introducing and adjusting regulations as the digital currency industry changes. Trials and surveys around CBDC design choices must also continue for policymakers to discover the likely impact on the economy and the response of the general public.

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1. Introduction

Central bank digital currency (CBDC) is a relatively new phenomenon which has rapidly developed over the last decade as technological advancements have widened the scope of potential for the currency. Multiple definitions exist for a CBDC; the Bank of England (2022a) simply defines CBDC as ‘money that a central bank, like the Bank of England, can produce [...] in the form of an amount on a computer or similar device’, and the International Monetary Fund defines CBDC as ‘a digital representation of a sovereign currency issued by and as a liability of a jurisdiction’s central bank or other monetary authority’ (Kiff, et al., 2020).

1.1. How does CBDC line up with the history of money?

Barrdear and Kumhoff (2021) note that there is ‘no historical experience from which to draw’ and little empirical material to help evaluate CBDC and understand its potential impact on society. However, Bordo (2021) describes that history proves that ‘monetary transformations [...] have been driven by changing technology’ amongst other factors and that ‘technological change in money and finance is inevitable’. Bordo and Flandreau (2001) also explain that central banks’ monetary policy tools have constantly evolved since the 17th century, and only in the last few decades has technology developed sufficiently to allow monetary authorities to operate credible fiat money regimes with low interest rates.

Central bank digital currency is undeniably a major innovation, with public access to the central balance sheet unmatched in the modern banking era. However, this access to the balance sheet is not unprecedented; many central banks previously allowed deposits by citizens as well as firms (Fernández-Villaverde, et al., 2020). Upon creation, the Bank of England initially engaged in commercial activities and acted similarly to a private bank. The central bank interacting solely with private banks is generally a post-WW2 phenomenon.

1.2. Types of CBDC

There are two main forms of CBDC that policymakers worldwide are considering. A wholesale CBDC would limit the use of CBDC to financial institutions, whereas a retail CBDC allows the general public to hold and use the currency. Although a wholesale CBDC would be less disruptive to the financial system and preserve financial architecture, a retail CBDC more effectively addresses many issues within the modern payment system and impacts the financial system more substantially (Ahya, et al., 2021).

Many institutions solely refer to retail CBDC when mentioning central bank digital currency, including the Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System (2020), which defines it as ‘a digital form of central bank money that is widely available to the general public’, excluding wholesale CBDC in their definition. Therefore, this paper will focus on the introduction of a retail CBDC into the economy.

1.3. What are the aims of CBDC?

For a CBDC to meet the criteria as a form of money, it must satisfy the functions of money. The primary function of money is to act as a medium of exchange, but most currencies are also stores of value and units of account.

The Bank of England (England’s central bank) must satisfy crucial objectives for public interest, including safety, integrity, efficiency, and access (Bank for International Settlements, 2021b). It does this by providing the unit of account in the monetary system, using its own balance sheet as the ultimate means of settlement, and overseeing the payment system’s integrity while upholding a competitive playing field. The Bank of England’s primary objective is to maintain monetary and financial stability (Bank of England, 2020). A CBDC must be implemented in this context.

The introduction of a CBDC would aim to improve financial stability, monetary policy implementation, financial inclusion, domestic and cross-border payments efficiency, and payments safety and robustness, among other factors. The importance of these goals differs across different countries depending on national economic characteristics such as their reliance on cash and the state of their banking systems.

A series of Bank for International Settlements (BIS) surveys show that emerging market economies describe domestic payments efficiency, financial inclusion, and payments safety as ‘very important’ motivations for issuing a retail CBDC (Boar and Wehrli, 2021). On the other hand, advanced economies only rank payments safety in that bracket. These surveys also reveal that these motivations increased in importance from 2018-2020.

Figure 1: The fundamental aims of a central bank digital currency

1.4. Why should a CBDC be introduced?

The recent explosion of cryptocurrencies and stablecoins has threatened the economy, especially the crucial principle of monetary sovereignty (Patel, et al., 2020). The Cambridge Dictionary (n.d.) defines cryptocurrency as 'a digital currency produced by a public network, rather than any government, that uses cryptography to make sure payments are sent and received safely'. Stablecoins are cryptocurrencies that peg their market value to an external currency (or asset such as gold).

A private digital currency, such as a cryptocurrency, circulating in the economy would have an impact on the central bank's control of the money supply. This could compromise the ubiquity of public money and reduce monetary sovereignty. It would also impair vital central bank functions, including weakening the reach of monetary policy and challenging the central bank's role as lender of last resort (Brunnermeier and Landau, 2022).

The central bank is currently falling behind the private sector over digital payment options, and CBDC is the most effective response for it to cement its role in the economy (Ahya, et al., 2021). While stablecoins and cryptocurrencies must operate subject to stringent government regulation, a well-designed CBDC could flourish as it 'would combine the efficiency of a digital payment instrument with the safety of central bank money' (European Central Bank, 2021). This would preserve monetary sovereignty and enhance the impact of monetary policy on the economy.

On top of this, the use of cash in the UK and many other major economies is dwindling, and CBDC would provide an alternative form of widely available central bank money (Bercetche, 2021). This move away from cash is occurring without government or central bank guidance, which therefore cannot manage the transition to ensure it is beneficial for the economy (Ward and Rochemont, 2019). Introducing a CBDC would allow the central bank to continue to produce sovereign money and would therefore be able to control this transformation.

Digitalisation also has added benefits, as it offers a medium to produce an efficient form of money with low transaction costs. CBDC would also be much cheaper than cash to manufacture, although the degree of this depends on the design choice of the ledger system, explained in [section 3.4](#).

2. The potential impact of a central bank digital currency

As discussed in the introduction, a retail CBDC would likely impact various sectors of the economy. It would compete to some extent with the private sector, especially commercial bank deposits, by providing an alternative form of payment. This competition impacts upon the entire banking sector by creating the potential for innovation but risking financial disintermediation. A CBDC may also facilitate bank runs in times of crisis, as people may move money out of deposit accounts and into a CBDC account. A common criticism of CBDC is that it may limit competition and innovation. A CBDC that dominates the payments sphere could crowd out the private sector and stifle both innovation and efficiency. This would most likely occur under a single-tier model (see [section 3.2.1](#)) in which the bank controls the entire CBDC system without financial intermediaries

2.1. Potential to promote continuous innovation

The Bank of England 'is committed to supporting innovation and improving how payments function' (Bank of England, 2021). An alliance between central banks and private sector financial institutions, which would occur under an intermediated CBDC (see [section 3.2.2](#)), would promote private sector innovation. Banks, FinTechs, and other financial sector institutions are best placed to use their expertise to enhance innovation, especially in the payments sphere, a department in which the central bank has less experience. As these institutions would control some parts of the CBDC, they would be motivated to continuously innovate the system under a competitive landscape to improve efficiency.

Improvements in technology have created the possibility to enhance both competition and innovation in the payments system. The payments landscape is continuously evolving, and

CBDC promotes future technological innovation to ensure transactions are efficient and low-cost.

2.2. Danger of bank disintermediation and financial instability

The primary risk of implementing a CBDC is that it may cause bank disintermediation. If CBDC replaces banknotes and not bank deposits in the economy, the banking system will continue to function as it does currently. However, if CBDC substitutes commercial bank deposits on a large scale, commercial banks would lose revenue and disintermediation of the banking sector would occur.

A well-designed CBDC could overpower the financial sector by offering safer, cheaper transactions and a higher interest rate while raising revenue via seignorage² (Soderberg, et al., 2022). It would also be backed by central bank reserves, making it risk-free, which other forms of money, such as bank deposits, do not offer. If a central bank introduced CBDC intending to be as efficient and attractive as possible, it would likely cause a substantial decrease in bank deposits, massively reducing the revenue of commercial banks which may not stay afloat.

Bank disintermediation is the most likely source of financial instability caused by CBDC. Commercial banks rely on interest income earned from bank deposits as a crucial source of revenue, income which would drastically decrease with disintermediation. These banks are major financial institutions, and their collapse could send shockwaves through the economy and potentially cause a financial crisis, as witnessed in 2008 (Barth, et al., 2012).

Structural bank disintermediation could worsen the transmission of monetary policy. If the central bank introduced a non-interest-bearing CBDC (see [section 3.5](#)), commercial bank deposits would remain the sole source of monetary policy transmission. In this system, reduced deposits in favour of holding CBDC would mean that monetary policy would have a lesser impact.

The consideration that CBDC must aim to play a small role in the banking sector arguably highlights the inefficiencies within that sector. Some claim that CBDC should intend to take over the banking sector and accept the potential short-term instability in favour of a more efficient system in the long term, in which the central bank becomes a monopoly creator of money. This is linked to the 'sovereign money' argument, which claims that taking power out of the banking system would improve stability and end boom-and-bust cycles (Huber, 2016). This argument is somewhat political and generally unpopular with policymakers, as it could have a disastrous short-term impact and may not be beneficial in the long-term. The

² Seignorage, also spelt seigniorage, is the profit the government makes from the difference between the value of money and the cost of producing and distributing it. It is traditionally related to government revenue from printing cash and banknotes but also applies to CBDC.

central bank's position in the economy would massively expand, and it may not be able to handle these new tasks. Many, including Foster and McChesney (2017), consider monopolies to create stagnation due to having no competition, whereas the competitive private sector is innovative as companies fight to become more efficient. For these reasons, Auer and Boehme (2021) and others argue that the central bank must maintain the two-tiered financial system and continue bank intermediation, as further discussed in [section 3.2](#).

2.3. Risk of facilitating bank runs

A financial crisis would exacerbate the potential for CBDC to crowd out bank deposits. During a crisis, a run on the banks from riskier deposits to safe, reserve-backed CBDC would seem likely. Although bank runs in recent history have been from weaker to stronger banks (Bindseil, 2020), this may be because it is awkward to transfer large quantities of commercial bank deposits into banknotes and liquid assets. Without limits or disincentives, CBDC would be much easier to convert deposits into, which would likely be the case.

However, as discussed in [section 3.5.2](#), design choices such as a cap on CBDC holdings or a two-tier remuneration system can prevent this from happening, and this should not be a problem for a well-designed CBDC.

2.4. Risk of digital dollarisation³

Historically, there have been two ways for a currency to internationalise: by becoming a global store of value or a medium of exchange for international transactions (Brunnermeier, et al., 2019). This phenomenon would threaten countries' monetary sovereignty as currency substitution would occur, meaning the domestic currency would become used less.

However, an account-based CBDC would have to be accepted for cross-border transactions by the issuing central bank and the receiving country, which is unlikely as most countries will look to protect their monetary sovereignty (a key motivation for implementing a CBDC). Also, identity verification soothes the fear that CBDC may circulate on the black market.

2.5. Impact on cross-border payments

A CBDC would increase the efficiency of cross-border payments, which are currently slow and inefficient. However, a retail CBDC would be primarily used for domestic purposes to avoid the risk of currency substitution that cross-border transactions bring, as discussed in

³ Dollarisation refers to the widespread domestic use of a foreign currency in daily transactions (Bank for International Settlements, 2021b).

[section 2.4](#). Therefore, it would likely require government cooperation for this form of CBDC to have cross-border potential, such as the mCBDC Bridge project mentioned in [section 4.3](#).

On the other hand, the central bank would likely implement a wholesale CBDC that helps to improve wholesale cross-border payments such as securities trading. However, it would not impact retail cross-border payments as the general public would not be able to use it (see [section 3.1](#)).

3. Design choices for central bank digital currency

As discussed in the introduction, there are multiple design choices for CBDC with differing impacts on the financial system. There is a chicken-and-egg type problem in which consumers can only use CBDC if merchants accept it, and merchants will only accept the currency if it is frequently used (Deutsche Bank, 2021). Therefore, to ensure it circulates in the economy, the central bank must design CBDC as an attractive form of payment, which may include having an efficient payment mechanism with low transaction fees. As analysed in [section 2](#), a retail CBDC would have a severe, possibly irreversible impact on the economy, so the potential consequences of each design choice must be fully understood when implementing the currency.

3.1. Wholesale, retail and synthetic CBDC

The first crucial design choice in introducing a CBDC is whether to introduce a wholesale or retail CBDC. As discussed in the introduction, this largely depends on the policy goals of the digital currency and the impact that policymakers want it to have.

3.1.1. Wholesale CBDC

A wholesale CBDC would make wholesale transactions, including interbank transfers, smoother and more efficient, and make the entire system more secure. It would have no visible impact on the general public, who would not hold or have any interaction with the digital currency. Implementing a wholesale CBDC would be a much easier option to design and would have a small, entirely positive impact on the financial system. It would create a more efficient payment system for the banking sector through atomic settlement⁴,

⁴ **Atomic settlement** means that, for a transfer of two assets, the transfer of one asset will only occur if the other transaction does too (Bank of England, 2018), improving the speed and security of transactions.

increasing resilience (Kalifa, 2021) and enhancing cross-border payments (Banque de France, et al., 2021).

3.1.2. Retail CBDC

On the other hand, implementing a retail CBDC would have a much more extensive impact on the financial system and the economy. It would give individuals direct access to central bank money, forming a new version of government-backed fiat money. If well designed, this would increase payment system efficiency by reducing transaction costs and potentially giving further impetus to further private sector innovation, improving the payment mechanism (Bank for International Settlements, 2021b). It will also strengthen the monetary sovereignty of the Bank of England, which a wholesale CBDC would fail to address. If an interest-bearing (see [section 3.5](#)) retail CBDC gained traction in the economy, it would improve monetary policy transmission, as central banks would directly be able to directly control the interest rates of money held by people (Kiff, et al., 2020).

Fewer central banks are contemplating issuing a wholesale than a retail CBDC. According to a 2021 survey, 68% of central banks consider it 'possible' or 'likely' that they will issue a retail CBDC in the medium term, compared to 54% for a wholesale CBDC (Kosse and Matte, 2021). While this number for retail CBDCs has almost doubled since the 2018 survey, it has only slowly increased for wholesale.

3.1.3. Synthetic CBDC

Another option would be to introduce a synthetic CBDC, also known as sCBDC, which allows e-money providers to hold and transact in central bank reserves. As with a retail CBDC, an sCBDC permits e-money holders to transact using a central bank-backed currency.

An sCBDC would be the least invasive version of CBDC, as the central bank would play a similar role as in the current banking system. This would mean not putting the central bank's reputation at risk (Adrian and Mancini-Griffoli, 2019) and allowing competition within the private sector, eliminating the risk of financial disintermediation.

However, an sCBDC would arguably not be a pure form of CBDC, as the end-user has no direct claim on the central bank, and is instead a form of narrow money (Bank for International Settlements, et al., 2020). It would not be controlled or regulated to the extent of CBDCs and would operate under profit motive rather than the public interest. It would also have a limited, neutral impact on the economy compared to a wholesale CBDC and, more majorly, a retail CBDC.

As stated in the introduction, this section will outline the design choices for a retail CBDC.

3.2. Intermediated vs unilateral system

The biggest issue with a retail CBDC is that it may cause financial disintermediation through deposit substitution by challenging commercial bank deposits.

Some, such as Huber (1999), aim for bank disintermediation and affirm that the central bank should have ‘unimpaired full control of the money supply’. This view is generally unsupported by policymakers, who argue that it would gravely damage monetary and financial stability (Burlon, et al., 2022).

The level of financial disintermediation created by CBDC would largely depend on its operating model. In designing the currency, the central bank can choose whether to control each step of its creation and implementation or create a tiered system, in which it outsources some tasks to financial intermediaries. These would include commercial banks and non-bank financial institutions. The four predominant steps are issuance, distribution, controlling payment services, and interacting with end-users (Kiff, et al., 2020).

3.2.1. Single-tiered CBDC

Under a single-tiered system, also known as a ‘unilateral’ CBDC (Soderberg, et al., 2022), the central bank would control all steps of the operational model. This approach would mean that users hold accounts directly at the central bank, which has total control over the process. It would favour financial inclusion by eliminating the fees that financial intermediaries would likely charge users (Patel, et al., 2020).

However, a single-tier model may detract from the central bank’s role as a ‘lean and focused public institution’ (Bank for International Settlements, 2021b), which would bear operational tasks that may ‘exceed the scope of its core mandate’ (Kiff, et al., 2020). Furthermore, the central bank does not have recent experience with end-user interaction, and inefficiencies may arise in its duties. A well-designed unilateral CBDC would likely cause financial disintermediation, as it would be more efficient than bank deposits, with lower fees, so would crowd out and reduce the revenue of commercial banks. In this situation, the central bank would be a ‘highly advantaged competitor’ in deposit collection, in ‘direct competition with banks’ (Pollock, 2018), who face strict regulation.

Figure 2: A diagram demonstrating how a typical transaction would occur using a single-tier retail CBDC

3.2.2. Intermediated CBDC

The more popular model among central banks is an intermediated CBDC (also known as a hybrid CBDC), in which the currency remains a central bank liability, but financial intermediaries handle some tasks (Ahya, et al., 2021). Financial intermediaries would include commercial banks and non-bank financial institutions, which would likely obtain revenue by charging payment fees (Soderberg, et al., 2022). This would somewhat mitigate the risk of financial disintermediation. Despite holding an account with an intermediary, the user would still have a legal claim on the central bank in a hybrid system.

Furthermore, this system would allow commercial banks to assume tasks similar to those they complete in the current financial system. These include interacting with users, maintaining a digital financial network and handling real-time payments. The central bank has little experience with many of these operations and may lack the infrastructure and expertise to run them smoothly and efficiently (Patel, et al., 2020).

Another issue is whether central banks should charge intermediaries for using the CBDC system, a choice linked to whether the central bank intends to recoup development costs. This decision also impacts end-users as intermediaries would likely pass these fees

downstream, making CBDC payments more expensive and less efficient, hampering initial policy goals (Soderberg, et al., 2022).

The central bank would also implement regulation surrounding whether intermediaries should be allowed to charge payment fees to users to obtain revenue. Allowing financial intermediaries acting as Payment Service Providers (PSPs) to charge fees on CBDC transactions would enable them to gain income, reducing the risk of financial disintermediation. However, making transactions more expensive would go against the policy goal of financial inclusion. Furthermore, this would further disconnect CBDC from its previous similarities with cash, which carried no additional transaction fees.

Figure 3: A diagram demonstrating how a typical transaction would occur using an intermediated retail CBDC

3.2.3. Multiple accounts system

Another option would be to allow users to have two accounts, one directly with the central bank and the other with a financial intermediary. This gives users the anonymity and security that comes with a central bank option while reducing the risk of financial disintermediation.

However, to ensure that consumers use the account with the intermediary, the CBDC account with the central bank should have limited functionality and a deposit limit (Ahya, et al., 2021). This system would make the central bank's account similar to cash, with no interest rates, while the private sector maintains a strong deposit base and gain revenue. The public account would also act as increased competition with the private sector, which is therefore compelled to innovate and offer incentives to potential customers.

3.3. Privacy and security

Observing the consumers' right to privacy is a key consideration of CBDC. In a survey conducted by the European Central Bank (ECB), privacy ranked as the highest requested feature for a potential digital euro (Brunnermeier and Landau, 2022). A large amount of information can be assumed from an individual's transaction history, including habits and medical issues. Cash transactions, which CBDC aims to imitate to an extent, offer complete anonymity.

3.3.1. Trade-off between privacy and security

Non-anonymous payment services harm the crucial policy aim of financial inclusion, as forms of identification can be expensive to obtain. However, there is somewhat of a trade-off between privacy and security, which ranked second in the ECB survey. The CBDC framework must comply with Anti-Money Laundering (AML) and Combating the Financing of Terrorism (CFT) regulations. Reporting requirements include the 'Know your customer' (KYC) regulation, which requires financial institutions to verify the identity of their users (Allen, et al., 2020). The CBDC network must comply with these. A key question surrounding this is which authority should be responsible for identifying users and validating transactions. Under a single-tiered system, the central bank would authenticate users, but under a hybrid model, financial intermediaries would likely be more suited to the task. This decision may also come down to the culture within the country: whether the private or public sector is more trusted in society.

However, the central bank and financial intermediary supporting the transaction (in a hybrid system) may not need to hold granular personal data on users, and the core ledger can store pseudonym accounts instead. Each account can then be linked to a Payment Interface Provider (PIP), which knows the identity of users and applies AML and CFT checks to

transactions (Bank of England, 2020). This system would reduce user privacy concerns whilst ensuring that regulatory standards are upheld. Furthermore, continuous improvements in the sphere of digital identity mean that improved models may arise.

3.3.2. Collecting user data

Another critical policy choice surrounding privacy is whether to allow transaction data to be collected (Bank of England, 2021). Such data would include spending patterns, which the central bank could use to improve its understanding of the state of the economy and the public's reaction to policy implementation.

If private intermediaries were allowed to collect the data (under the hybrid model), they could gain revenue by selling the information to other institutions, which would use it to target specific products to users, as they do in the current banking setup (Mastercard, 2022). Allowing financial intermediaries to collect and sell user data would increase their revenue, helping to decrease the risk of financial disintermediation, but at the cost of reduced privacy for users.

In practice, actual payment choices do not align with research claiming that privacy is of utmost importance (Deutsche Bank, 2021). A study completed by the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) shows that people rarely maintain these privacy requirements if a system offers some incentive or is easier to operate (Athey, et al., 2017).

However, other surveys show that users rarely switch providers, even when it is easy and saves money (Adams, et al., 2021). A CBDC must, therefore, be very attractive to consumers for them to make the switch. An efficient, easy-to-use CBDC system with low transaction costs may offer this alone, but securing user data may help to entice users. Furthermore, financial intermediaries would receive most of their revenue from transaction fees and should not require additional income from collecting user data to stay afloat.

In a Financial Conduct Authority (2015) survey, respondents claimed that convenience and a reputable provider are the most important factors when choosing an easy-access account, so ensuring the identification process is simple would be very important to popularising CBDC. Many modern commercial banks, such as Monzo, use online user verification, meaning a customer must take a photo of their ID document and a short video of themselves. This is a quick and easy process, which uses biometrics, and claims to be more secure than face-to-face interactions (Electronic Identification, 2021). However, biometric templates must be used with caution, as the database makes for an enticing target for hackers.

3.4. Centralised vs decentralised ledger system

Central banks must choose which type of ledger system to run CBDC on, linked to the fundamental choice of having an account-based or tokenised CBDC. An account-based CBDC runs on a centralised ledger system, in which a user holds an account directly with the central bank (or with a financial intermediary, as discussed in [section 3.2](#)). On the other hand, tokenisation involves users holding ‘wallets’, usually based on decentralised distributed ledger technology. Each system has benefits and drawbacks, and this decision may massively impact the extent to which CBDC is accepted.

3.4.1. Distributed ledger technology

Tokenisation refers to recording assets, currency in this context, in a token form on a decentralised ledger system. This system would be very similar to cash in that it preserves the anonymity of transactions but could also enable illicit use.

Distributed Ledger Technology, also known as DLT, is a decentralised ledger system on which most digital currencies (and assets) are currently based, and became popular by overcoming a lack of trust in central authority (Kiff, et al., 2020). Blockchain, a form of DLT, is the underlying technology behind major stablecoins and cryptocurrencies, such as Bitcoin (see [section 5](#)). In a system which relies on blockchain, data is recorded on ledgers and gathered in blocks, which are secured using cryptographic keys⁵. Every node in the network holds all transaction information, meaning that if one node falters, the network still functions in its ability to validate transactions.

Different types of blockchain allow varying levels of public access; a private blockchain has a low number of nodes and gives a single entity full control over the ledger, a permissioned blockchain has more nodes and gives multiple entities this privilege, and a public blockchain often has thousands of nodes, and gives unrestricted access to the public (Allen, et al., 2022). The focus of institutions in both the private and public sectors researching DLTs is on the permissioned system (World Bank Group, 2017).

Blockchain, and DLT as a whole, has multiple potential benefits related to digital transactions. It can bolster international trade by improving the efficiency of cross-border payments while reducing trading costs. On top of this, it may reduce the number of problem transactions by providing a transparent ledger system which makes payments more secure. It is also a very safe system, as an ingrained feature is that it is ‘almost impossible to hack’ (Dinh and Thai, 2018). These factors make it a seemingly attractive ledger system on which to base CBDC.

⁵ Cryptographic keys are bits of information used to encrypt and decrypt data. In the case of cryptocurrencies, if the key is lost or stolen, the user has no way of accessing their wallet.

However, future technological advancements will likely challenge this presently impenetrable system, especially as it makes a very appealing target to potential hackers. Byzantine failures and issues of double-spend also occur in the blockchain system, and there are questions of scalability with the solution of Byzantine Fault Tolerance (Kannengießner, et al., 2020).

Moreover, DLT has a significantly slower transaction speed than other systems. Bitcoin uses a public blockchain with a very high number of nodes, meaning that the average transactions per second (TPS) is between 3-4, which is extremely low. On the other hand, VISA, which is a centralised system, averages over 1600 TPS (Mechkarosa, et al., 2018). Due to this, DLT may face scalability issues, as its current form has proven slow and inefficient. Although a private blockchain can handle over 1000 TPS, it faces security problems due to having few nodes. This trade-off is largely unavoidable.

Furthermore, transactions on blockchain are very energy-intensive. Bitcoin, notorious for its high energy consumption, uses over 700kWh per transaction, whilst Ethereum, another cryptocurrency, uses over 60kWh (Schmidt, 2021). On the other hand, 100,000 VISA transactions consume under 150kWh (Bach, et al., 2018). Energy-intensive ledger systems are both expensive to run and environmentally damaging.

Figure 4: Discussing the primary benefits and drawbacks of using a Blockchain ledger system

3.4.2. Centralised ledger system

A centralised, account-based ledger system would be the easiest to implement. It would involve opening an account directly with the central bank or with a financial intermediary, as discussed in [section 3.2](#). This system would be much more efficient than DLT, as it would allow for more, quicker transactions. It would also be easier to implement verification which would help to uphold regulatory standards and prevent fraud.

Whether to implement an account-based, centralised ledger system or DLT is linked to the trade-off between privacy and security. A centralised system would likely be more secure, as it would be easier to verify users. This verification does not have to come at the expense of privacy. Authenticated data structures (ADS) use cryptography to allow verification without giving away personal details (Allen, et al., 2020). Additionally, it makes the system more secure and reduces the likelihood of double-spend problems or transactional failures. It would also be much cheaper and less energy-intensive to run than DLT. Decentralisation is attractive in theory but very difficult to implement effectively.

Figure 5: Discussing the primary benefits and drawbacks of using a centralised ledger system

3.5. Remunerated CBDC

Another crucial policy choice is whether to introduce a remunerated (interest-bearing) CBDC or a non-interest-bearing currency which would mimic cash. An interest-bearing CBDC would allow the central bank to transmit monetary policy directly to holders of the currency, improving its efficiency and impact. An interest rate on CBDC similar to that offered to commercial banks would also directly compete with bank deposits, forcing banks to raise their deposit rates so increasing financial inclusion (Fatas, et al., 2019).

3.5.1. Negative interest rates

An interest-bearing CBDC would allow the central bank to implement negative interest rates, eliminating the liquidity trap⁶ by overcoming the Zero Lower Bound (ZLB)⁷. Negative interest rates would be a useful monetary tool to control inflation. Another tool would be helpful to the central bank, as interest rates are currently hampered by the liquidity trap, while quantitative easing has proved largely ineffective (Giansante, et al., 2020).

However, there are questions as to whether this would be effective if cash continues to exist in the economy, as it offers people a way out of facing negative interest rates. Some argue that the central bank should phase cash out after introducing a CBDC, although this would likely face resistance (Kiel Institute for the World Economy, 2018).

It is also possible that interest rates on CBDC function as much as an incentive to hold, or not hold, the digital currency as one to improve monetary policy transmission. CBDC should aim to become ubiquitous in the economy but not substitute bank deposits, causing financial disintermediation, essentially trying to satisfy the 'goldilocks principle'. A flexible interest rate, which the central bank would implement separately from the bank rate, has the power to make CBDC more or less attractive. A low or negative interest rate on CBDC, far below the bank rate, could help to reduce the risk of financial disintermediation by giving commercial banks a competitive advantage.

3.5.2. Two-tiered remuneration system

As previously discussed, one criticism of CBDC is that it may cause financial disintermediation by competing with bank deposits. During times of crisis, CBDC may facilitate runs on the bank by providing an alternative to commercial bank deposits, which will exacerbate these threats (see [section 2.3](#)). One solution to this problem would be to introduce a cap on CBDC holdings, removing its 'store of value' function. The system would automatically reject any transfers into an account which takes the balance over the limit.

⁶ A liquidity trap means that monetary policy becomes weaker as interest rates approach zero. A reduction in the bank rate is less effective when interest rates are lower.

⁷ The Zero Lower Bound refers to 0% interest rates, which the bank rate cannot reach in the current financial system.

Alternatively, a waterfall solution would transfer the excess to a linked deposit account held with a commercial bank. For these arrangements to work effectively, the central bank would have to introduce regulation that ensures individuals cannot hold multiple wallets with different institutions (or ensures that separate wallets are linked to the same account, depending on policy choices) (Patel, et al., 2020).

Alternatively, under an interest-bearing CBDC, central banks could implement a tiered remuneration system in which they charge holdings above a certain threshold at a significantly lower interest rate. This would effectively assign the payment function of money to the first tier and the store of value function to the second tier, which would disincentivise holding the currency through a zero or negative interest rate (Bindseil, 2020). It is possible that a negative interest rate may scare people off from holding CBDC. Therefore, to ensure people maintain confidence in the system, the central bank could announce that it will never implement negative interest rates on the first tier.

3.6. Offline capabilities of a CBDC

For a CBDC to be an effective form of payment in the economy, it must offer 24/7 offline transactions. Firstly, offline payments help to attain the policy goal of financial inclusion, as many cannot afford constant internet access or may be in places with limited internet connection. They would be even more important in countries which face natural disasters that cause network outages. Offline payments would also be essential in maintaining the de-networked feature of cash, which is widely available in commercial banking. The Bank of England (2020) recognises this and claims that no offline capabilities 'would limit the usability and usefulness of CBDC'. It also recognises the challenge of creating a CBDC with the capacity for offline transactions that remains secure and private.

An interest-bearing CBDC may face some problems with offline accounts, which would be unable to acknowledge a change in interest rates. (Shah, et al., 2020) recommends using an onboard time clock to calculate interest or requiring users to connect to a network after a set period of time or number of transactions.

VISA has released a white paper in which they propose an offline payment system under an intermediated CBDC structure (Christodorescu, et al., 2021). This system would not be able to function on DLT.

3.7. Interoperability with the current payment system

To ensure that financial disintermediation does not occur, a CBDC must be able to interact with the current payment system. For a CBDC to be accepted into the economy, it must be convertible into and out of other forms of money, including bank deposits (Brunnermeier

and Landau, 2022). A CBDC infrastructure interoperable with the existing payment structure could reduce settlement risks, enhance liquidity and promote competition. It would strengthen the role of the central bank and improve the domestic payment ecosystem (Patel, et al., 2020).

On top of the more obvious convertibility aspect, interoperability means ensuring that CBDC does not dominate the payments sphere. As discussed in [section 3.5.1](#), there is a fine line between ubiquity and dominance, which a CBDC must not cross if bank intermediation is desired.

Interoperability with the domestic system also supports innovation. It could set the foundation for international coordination and enhance the potential of cross-border payments.

4. Projects & pilots

This section will outline the structure of numerous CBDCs already implemented worldwide, as well as pilot schemes and the perspective of different countries on CBDCs. It will also discuss some projects which have outlined potential CBDC structures.

Atlantic Council has published a continuously updated [Central Bank Digital Currency Tracker](#), which tracks how close each country is to implementing a CBDC. It also shows which type of CBDC each country is researching and the underlying technology and architecture.

The tracker shows that most countries are undecided on the underlying technology to use (DLT, centralised ledger or both) and whether to use an intermediary. Most of these countries are researching a retail CBDC, and most are in the ‘research’ or ‘development’ stage. The UK is in the ‘research’ stage of both a wholesale and intermediated retail CBDC. Eleven countries have launched a CBDC as of November 2022, the first of which was the Bahamas.

4.1. The Bahamian Sand Dollar

The Sand Dollar is a retail CBDC issued in the Bahamas that, like the Bahamian Dollar, is pegged 1 to 1 to the US dollar. It is the first retail CBDC implemented worldwide and aims to strengthen security, increase the efficiency of payments, and improve financial inclusion within the country (Sand Dollar, 2022). In the Bahamas, commercial bank usage is noticeably low in rural areas, despite the vast majority of people owning smartphones (Wyss, 2021).

The Sand Dollar relies on an intermediated, account-based system that runs on a form of distributed ledger technology owned and updated directly by the central bank (Soderberg, et al., 2022), which uses authorised financial institutions (AFIs) for transactions. These AFIs include commercial banks, payment service providers (PSPs), and other businesses. However, when the Sand Dollar launched, many commercial banks and other institutions were unprepared and sceptical as they perceived digital currency as a threat to the banking system. *Island Pay*, a PSP, were among the first to upgrade its infrastructure and facilitate the Sand Dollar. Demand for the CBDC was high from launch, but there were initial technical challenges as many institutions were not yet ready to support it (Project Management Institute, 2021).

An International Monetary Fund (2021) report found that the Sand Dollar ‘has the potential to help foster financial inclusion and payment system resilience in the event of a natural disaster’. However, the COVID pandemic has limited the currency's reach, as many citizens and businesses remain uninformed of its potential benefits. It also states that the Bahamian central bank should strengthen cybersecurity and resilience of the CBDC network both to safeguard financial integrity and ensure it is fully resilient against natural disasters, which are common in the region. The currency is non-interest-bearing, so its impact on certain aspects of the economy is somewhat limited.

4.2. The Nigerian eNaira

The eNaira first was launched solely to bank account holders in October 2021, but it soon became available to the entire population. It is a retail, intermediated CBDC which relies on DLT.

The primary aim of the project was to increase financial inclusion from 64% to the target of 95%, and eNaira is projected to increase GDP by \$29bn over the next decade (if well-run) (Atlantic Council, 2022). By December 2021, over 600,000 eNaira wallets had been created, and at an event in August 2022, the governor of the central bank of Nigeria claimed that eNaira had recorded 4 billion naira (over £8 million) worth of transactions (Guardian Nigeria, 2022). This shows that the currency has been well accepted and has circulated in the Nigerian economy.

Like the sand dollar, it is non-interest-bearing, and a remunerated eNaira may have further assisted the policy goal of financial inclusion. Other objectives of the eNaira include making transactions cheaper and ensuring that payments are secure.

4.3. Multiple CBDC Bridge project

The Bank for International Settlements (BIS) Innovation Hub has proposed a Multiple CBDC (mCBDC) Bridge project, which aims to facilitate and speed up cross-border transactions by

‘building a multi CBDC platform for international payments’ (Bank for International Settlements, 2021a). It recognises that cross-border payments are extremely slow in their current form, often taking a few days for each transaction to settle, and recognises the potential of a wholesale CBDC to speed them up and provide increased interoperability between nations.

The current mBridge model is a cooperation between central bank authorities of Hong Kong, Thailand, China and the United Arab Emirates and relies on DLT. It aims to ‘enhance efficiency, lower transaction costs and streamline regulatory compliance’ between the nations, which benefits international trade and capital market transactions amongst other business use cases.

The mCBDC Bridge project has the potential to expand across Asia and into Europe. Alternatively, other cross-border payment infrastructures may form in the future. Central banks should look to be at the forefront of these projects and not get left behind.

4.4. Project Hamilton

The Federal Reserve Bank of Boston and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology’s Digital Currency Initiative have combined to develop a hypothetical CBDC (Digital Currency Initiative, 2022). This includes designing a flexible transaction processing system which can support multiple CBDC models. A more detailed insight into the project is available [here](#).

Its goals include:

- A very high transaction speed, aiming for 100,000 transactions per second, scalable to handle hundreds of millions of users
- Resiliency, including ensuring the system continues to function at a high level, even with multiple data centre failures
- Privacy, for which the system aims to limit data access in the central transaction processor.
- Facilitating the role of an intermediary

A recent whitepaper produced by the Digital Currency Initiative providing an in-depth explanation of the Hamilton system design, available [here](#), describes and addresses the challenges, the security model, and the transaction design system (Digital Currency Initiative, 2022).

Notably, the project found that a blockchain-based system would struggle to match these goals, as it has operational complexities and lower performance than other systems. However, it notes that Blockchain performance is improving, and the system has the potential to support the CBDC models in which intermediaries run nodes in the system that validate and execute transactions.

The project also explains that the central bank does not need to retain all transaction information to implement a secure CBDC system, just ‘commitments to unspent funds’. It also recognises zero-knowledge proofs⁸ as having the potential to publish transactions executed without making them visible and compromising user-to-user privacy.

4.5. How to test and improve CBDC

The UK will launch a regulatory sandbox⁹ for testing DLT projects under regulators’ supervision in 2023 (Competition Policy International, 2022), which aims to increase the use of DLT and make financial markets more innovative. This sandbox will support crypto and stablecoin projects and give regulators a better understanding of what must be done to prepare for digital currencies. It will also offer more insight into DLT and to what extent it would be a viable ledger system for a CBDC.

If this sandbox tested a retail CBDC, it would give a better perspective on its likely impact. It could also provide information about how to design the digital currency and whether the chosen system for the sandbox would be effective.

4.6. Project New Era

Project New Era is a UK-based pilot led by the Digital FMI Consortium, which aims to evaluate the path towards a CBDC in the UK (Digital FMI Consortium, 2022). Phase one of the pilot culminated in a [paper](#) published in February 2022 that addressed challenges relating to CBDC. Phase two of the project will involve implementing a pilot scheme, which will aim to provide empirical data to policymakers and regulators on design choices. The pilot scheme will feature a stablecoin asset, *dSterling*, which is not a CBDC but shares many framework properties. This project is very important in ensuring that the UK does not fall behind while the US accelerates CBDC research and Panetta (2022) of the ECB announces that a Digital Euro is ‘likely to become a necessity’.

5. Cryptocurrencies and stablecoins

Many cryptocurrencies and stablecoins have become increasingly popular, and technological advancements have given them the potential to become a legitimate form of

⁸ Zero-knowledge proofs allow authentication without revealing details of either party or the information itself.

⁹ A regulatory sandbox is an environment in which products can be tested on consumers, which allows more information to be understood whilst limiting potential consequences.

money. The most popular cryptocurrency is Bitcoin, which can be used for some digital transactions. Regulation of cryptocurrency has recently increased, but many governments and central banks are unsure how to classify it. The ECB does not consider Bitcoin a currency and instead labels it a 'highly speculative asset' (Blanch, et al., 2021). Its price is extremely volatile, influenced by factors such as social media posts.

Stablecoins are a form of cryptocurrency that aim to keep their value stable and are pegged to a fiat currency or crypto-asset. Unlike other cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin, they are backed by assets, so many are able to maintain value.

Cryptocurrency and stablecoins could threaten monetary sovereignty if improperly regulated, as they have the potential to become dominant worldwide currencies that easily facilitate cross-border payments and are almost entirely anonymous. A well-designed CBDC combined with robust regulation would stop this possibility, which would likely not become a major threat if managed correctly.

CBDC is a disrupting force against this explosion in cryptocurrency growth, described as acting like 'streets and sunlight, a most effective policeman and disinfectant' (Cioroianu, et al., 2022). It is backed by central bank reserves, whereas cryptocurrencies are often completely unbacked, and stablecoins are essentially only as good as the issuer's promise. It is risk-free and flexible, whereas crypto is a regulated, risky investment, and stablecoins are also subject to regulation.

5.1. Diem (also known as Libra)

In 2019, Meta (formerly Facebook) released a stablecoin named 'Libra', backed by a large basket of assets such as fiat currencies (CFI Team, 2022). It aimed to become a primary medium of exchange for online transactions, which would be fast, secure and stable. It was renamed 'Diem' in 2020 after a regulatory backlash, in an attempt to show 'organisational independence'. However, the project failed and shut down, as Meta sold the infrastructure in 2022 for \$200m (Kwan, 2022).

The project was somewhat of a wake-up call to authorities, who were initially unprepared to regulate and manage it. It also demonstrates that large institutions can release digital currencies, and an influx of stablecoins is a serious possibility in the economy.

The CEO stated that they shut down the project as 'it became clear from our dialogue with federal regulators that the project could not move ahead' (TechXplore, 2020). This shows the wish of authorities to impose heavy regulation on these projects. It also improves the case for introducing a CBDC, which could stop stablecoins from becoming a threat.

5.2. Petro

In 2018, the Venezuelan government launched a stablecoin called 'Petro', which is backed by the state and pegged to the price of oil. It was introduced as an alternative to the Venezuelan Bolivar, which suffered massive hyperinflation and was almost worthless. The Petro, on the other hand, intended to provide stability, with a value linked to the price of a barrel of Venezuelan oil.

However, Petro immediately faced international sanctions, with the U.S. banning its citizens from engaging with the currency in any form. A senior U.S. administration official claimed that 'the Petro is a desperate effort by a corrupt regime to defraud international investors'. It is important to recognise that this is one of the many sanctions the U.S. has placed on Venezuela, which may be part of a conflict of ideology as much as an attack on the Petro itself.

6. Implications for policymakers

Policymakers must be aware of the likely impact of each design choice and how the wider financial landscape evolves with innovation in the payments sphere. They must be ready to introduce and adjust regulation over time and cannot fall behind in the rapidly changing digital currency industry.

6.1. Privacy and accountability

Policymakers must make a firm decision on the level of privacy that a CBDC offers its users, which, as discussed in [section 3.3.1](#), is subject to security regulation. The UK is a member of the Financial Action Task Force (FATF), which oversees the compliance of AML and CFT requirements. Therefore, the Bank of England must observe these regulations and cannot amend them to accommodate CBDC infrastructure.

Another vital decision is whether the central bank or intermediaries should collect user data. The Data Protection Act (DPA) protects consumers from having their data processed in ways deemed unfair or unlawful but does allow data collection. Commercial banks currently collect transactional data, which they use to learn more about consumers. They also sell personal data to third parties. The Bank of England (2022b) currently processes personal data for regulatory purposes and to inform policy-making. However, CBDC would offer the Bank of England to collect more invasive transactional data, which may be unpopular.

More trials and surveys need to be completed in this area before policymakers decide which entities are allowed to collect transactional data and what they can do with it. Although

commercial banks publicly collect and sell data to third parties, many people fear government surveillance, and a system in which the central bank collects personal data may not be well-received by the general public.

6.2. Financial stability

For a single-tiered CBDC to function without causing financial disintermediation, the central bank could use the income earned via seignorage to ‘compensate’ commercial banks, which they could use to invest (Fatas, et al., 2019). However, many would disagree with this system of artificially propping up the banking system, which would likely be inefficient and widely considered a misallocation of resources.

Under a hybrid CBDC system, banks would likely act as intermediaries, so could recoup revenue lost from a reduction in bank deposits. The short-term impact on commercial banks’ income is uncertain, but they will likely lose some revenue to non-bank competition. In the medium and long term, a larger percentage of bank revenue may come from loans and non-interest income in a move away from traditional bank activities. Non-interest income is revenue earned from non-core activities (deposits and loans) and includes investment banking and trading revenue. This shift has already started to occur over the last couple of decades. Studies show that a reliance on non-interest income in countries with a low concentration of banks, such as the UK, can increase systematic risk in the economy (Engle, et al., 2014). Therefore, policymakers should be wary of this shift and must regularly scrutinise regulation to ensure it does not cause long-term financial instability.

To prevent the mass substitution of bank deposits to CBDC and to mitigate the facilitation of bank runs, a cap on CBDC holdings or a multi-tiered remuneration system could be implemented, as discussed in [section 3.5.2](#). These methods would likely prevent bank disintermediation but may also make the currency less attractive. Policymakers should research and trial these functions to better understand how the cap or tiers should be structured and at what amount the cut-off should be (e.g. £3000).

These problems and solutions are based on the notion that bank disintermediation would lead to severe financial instability. However, there is a growing consideration that banks are no longer ‘too big to fail’ in the economy, as shareholders and investors now bear the cost of bank failure, not the central bank and taxpayers. The Bank of England declared that a major UK bank is able to fail safely, without lasting disruption to the economy, thanks to prudential regulation and a ‘robust resolution regime’ (Bank of England, 2022b). Although this would reduce confidence in the banking sector, it means that commercial banks do not hold the power they once did, and the thought of financial disintermediation is not as scary as it once was. More research needs to be done on its impact on the modern financial sector, but policymakers should bear in mind the possibility of allowing some bank disintermediation to occur when designing a CBDC.

6.3. Banking and financial regulation

The CBDC network would be designed to support policy choices, and policymakers must implement financial regulation to consolidate it. For example, for an intermediated model, a regulatory framework may support a cap on merchant fees. The decision as to whether charges can be implemented solely to merchants or also for peer-to-peer (p2p) transactions impacts the extent to which CBDC challenges financial inclusion, which is a crucial policy objective.

In a hybrid model, regulation must ensure that a large chunk of market power does not fall into the hands of a few companies. The primary benefit of using private sector intermediaries is that it enables competition and innovation. If any firm gains monopoly power, the system will be inefficient. Regulators must, therefore, maintain low barriers to entry and promote competition.

However, the relevant regulatory framework would likely need to be updated or redrawn to facilitate a CBDC and uphold standards to protect users. Additionally, current regulation surrounding these financial institutions is more strict on banks than non-banks. To improve competition within the sector, and in the interest of fairness, the central bank must instate the same CBDC-related regulation for all intermediaries.

6.4. Central bank policy effectiveness

CBDC could improve or worsen monetary policy effectiveness, depending on its design and regulation. The potential structural bank disintermediation associated with a non-interest-bearing CBDC could negatively impact monetary policy transmission. This would occur as fewer people would hold interest-bearing bank deposits, so the impact of monetary policy would be weaker. Policymakers must be wary of this and should consider introducing measures such as a cap on CBDC holdings discussed in [section 6.3](#) to ensure that the transmission mechanism through bank deposits has a sufficient impact on the economy.

On the other hand, an interest-bearing CBDC would improve monetary policy effectiveness, as discussed in [section 3.5](#). This would occur due to central bank-controlled interest rates directly impacting users' currency holdings, combined with the potential of negative interest rates, unprecedented in the UK. Under this system, the central bank can use interest rates to enhance or reduce the attractiveness of CBDC holdings compared to bank deposits. An interest rate on CBDC much lower than the bank rate would likely push consumers towards holding bank deposits. On the other hand, interest rates on CBDC similar to or higher than bank deposits would likely cause users to increase their CBDC holdings. This tool means that the central bank has some control over the quantity of CBDC held by users, meaning it can regulate financial intermediation to an extent.

6.5. Geopolitical consequences

The power of CBDC could allow currencies to establish global dominance. It is unlikely that this would be in the form of digital dollarisation, as discussed in [section 2.4](#), but the opportunity arises for a CBDC to cement its place as the world's reserve currency. This is especially true for the U.S. dollar, which currently accounts for over 50% of the world's foreign exchange reserves (International Monetary Fund, 2022). However, this position is in decline and under threat from the Chinese renminbi (Subramanian, 2011). The Federal Reserve System (2022) claimed that 'a U.S.-issued CBDC could [help] preserve the dominant international role of the U.S. dollar'. If the U.S. does not introduce a CBDC but other countries that play a significant role in the global financial system, such as China, do, their international position would be threatened. However, this would be very unlikely, and a U.S.-issued CBDC designed to promote global holdings would strengthen its international role. Policymakers in the U.K. should be wary of the potential international expansion of the dollar and must be ready to update the regulatory framework surrounding foreign currency to maintain monetary sovereignty.

As discussed in [section 4.3](#), central banks must cooperate on CBDC design research to allow interoperability on issues such as cross-border payments. The central banks of Canada, Japan, Sweden, Switzerland, the U.K and the U.S. collaborated with the European Central Bank and the BIS on [a CBDC report](#). This cooperation must continue to facilitate efficient cross-border payments and not allow one central bank digital currency to become the standard for international transactions. A dominant currency for cross-border purchases would overcomplicate the payments system and could significantly impact monetary sovereignty. Policymakers must be aware of the dangers of this prospect.

7. Conclusion

Central bank digital currency is evidently a superior form of money; its ability to act as a secure store of value, a stable unit of account, and a fast, widely available, inclusive medium of exchange for online and in-person transactions is unrivalled. A well-designed, interest-bearing retail CBDC would support monetary policy and vital objectives such as financial inclusion and economic stability. It could also potentially enhance cross-border payment efficiency in the long run and protect monetary sovereignty against the increasing threat of cryptocurrencies and stablecoins. On top of this, it would reduce transaction costs and promote innovation within the payments sphere.

The main concern of a CBDC is its potential to cause financial instability. The primary case for this is that CBDC could cause bank disintermediation, especially in a single-tier design. It

could also facilitate bank runs, which would be possible if there was no cap or tiered remuneration system on CBDC holdings. The risk of bank runs must be addressed by the design choices of a CBDC, as a significant shift away from bank deposits in a short period of time would likely cause severe financial instability.

However, the extent to which bank disintermediation would cause instability in the modern financial system is unclear, and more research needs to be carried out on this. If disintermediation appears to have a pronounced impact on financial stability, policymakers should design the system in a way that protects bank deposits. If not, they could create a CBDC which competes with bank deposits or aims to phase them out entirely in the long term.

The most effective design for a CBDC would be a retail, intermediated, remunerated system which allows negative interest rates and relies on centralised ledger technology. This system must offer offline payments and use a PIP to give users privacy while facilitating regulation requirements. The intermediated account should have a two-tiered remuneration system, in which the first tier has a relatively high interest rate, just below the bank rate, but the second tier has a lower interest rate. The difference in interest rates depends on the extent to which bank disintermediation impacts the economy and how vital maintaining bank deposits is in preserving financial stability. Subject to future surveys and studies, this model recommends that intermediaries should be allowed to collect transactional data, which they can use for private purposes and must send to the central bank, but should not be allowed to sell to third parties. A second account with limited capabilities, including no interest rates and a deposit limit, should also be offered with the central bank, as discussed in [section 3.2.3](#). The central bank should utilise user data from this account and the intermediated one to learn about consumer habits and reactions to policy. The two-account system provides flexibility for the future, as the central bank has the power to promote (or phase out) either account to adjust to changing policy goals.

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9. Table of literature

	<i>Name of paper</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Publisher / Journal</i>	<i>Central topic</i>
General overview of CBDC					
1	III. CBDCs: An Opportunity for the Monetary System	Bank for International Settlements	2021	BIS Annual Economic Report	Monetary System
2	Central Bank Digital Currencies: Costs, Benefits and Major Implications for the U.S. Economic System	Baer	2021	Bank Policy Institute Staff Working Paper	Impact on U.S.
3	Central Bank Digital Currency: Opportunities, Challenges and Design: A Discussion Paper	Bank of England	2020	BoE Discussion Paper	Opportunities
4	A Survey of Research on Retail Central Bank Digital Currency	Kiff et al	2020	IMF Working Papers	Considerations
5	Central Bank Digital Currencies	Sun	2020	Journal of Digital Banking	Understanding CBDCs
6	Understanding Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDC)	Ward & Rochemont	2019	Institute and Faculty of Actuaries	Understanding CBDCs & underlying technology
Macroeconomic impact of CBDC					
7	Digital Disruption: The Inevitable Rise of CBDC	Ahya et al	2021	Research Article	Impact on financial system
8	The Macroeconomics of Central Bank Digital Currencies	Barrdear & Kumhof	2021	Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control	Macroeconomic consequences
9	Tiered CBDC and the Financial System	Bindseil	2020	ECB Working Paper Series	Two-tier remuneration
10	The Optimal Quantity of CBDC in a Bank-Based Economy	Burlon et al	2022	ECB Working Paper	Quantitative analysis
11	Central Bank Digital Currency: Central Banking for All?	Fernández-Villaverde et al	2021	Review of Economic Dynamics	Impact on financial system
12	Plain Money: A Proposal for Supplying the Nations with the Necessary Means in a Modern Monetary System	Huber	1999	SSOAR Open Access Repository	Sovereign money
13	Sovereign Money: Beyond Reserve Banking	Huber	2016	Palgrave Macmillan	Sovereign money
14	The Benefits and Costs of a Central Bank Digital Currency for Monetary Policy	Nelson	2021	Bank Policy Institute	Impact on monetary policy
15	Exploring the Monetary Policy and Financial Stability Implications of Central Bank Digital Currencies	Panetta	2022	Speech at IESE Business School Banking Initiative Conference on Technology and Finance	Impact on monetary policy and financial stability
CBDC design choices					
16	Design Choices for a Central Bank Digital Currency: Policy and Technical Considerations	Allen et al	2020	Global Economy & Development	Policy considerations
17	The Digital Privacy Paradox: Small Money, Small Costs, Small Talk	Athey et al	2017	National Bureau of Economic Research	Privacy

18	Central Bank Digital Currency: The Quest for Minimally Invasive Technology	Auer & Boehme	2021	Bank for International Settlements	Ledger infrastructure choices
19	Privacy in CBDC Technology	Darba & Arora	2020	Bank of Canada Staff Analytical Note	Privacy
20	Regulating Central Bank Digital Currencies: Towards a Conceptual Framework	Hess	2020	SSRN Electronic Journal	Regulation
21	Technology Approach for a CBDC	Shah et al	2020	Bank of Canada Staff Analytical Note	Infrastructure choices
CBDC projects and pilots					
22	Multiple CBDC (MCBDC) Bridge	Bank for International Settlements	2021	BIS Innovation Hub	mCBDC
23	Project Helvetia: Settling Tokenised Assets in Central Bank Digital Currency	Bank for International Settlements et al	2020	BIS Innovation Hub	Project Helvetia
24	Project Jura: Cross-Border Settlement Using Wholesale CBDC	Banque de France et al	2021	BIS Innovation Hub	Wholesale CBDC
25	Towards a Two-Tier Hierarchical Infrastructure: An Offline Payment System for Central Bank Digital Currencies	Christodorescu et al	2020		Offline payment system design
26	Project Hamilton – Building a Hypothetical Central Bank Digital Currency	Digital Currency Initiative	2022	MIT Media Lab	Infrastructure choices
27	Staff Concluding Statement of the 2022 Article IV Mission	International Monetary Fund	2021	IMF Concluding Statement	Sand Dollar
28	A High Performance Payment Processing System Designed for Central Bank Digital Currencies	Lovejoy et al	2022	Digital Currency Initiative	Infrastructure choices
29	A New Era for Money	The Payments Association et al	2022	Project New Era Green Paper	Public-private partnership
The economic impacts of digital money & Fintech					
30	The Rise of Digital Money	Adrian & Mancini-Griffoli	2019	FinTech Notes	Implications of digital money
31	New Forms of Digital Money	Bank of England	2021	BoE Discussion Paper	Bank of England's thoughts
32	Central Bank Digital Currency in Historical Perspective: Another Crossroad in Monetary History	Bordo	2021	NBER Working Paper	CBDC from historical standpoint
33	The Digital Euro: Policy Implications and Perspectives	Brunnermeier & Landau	2022	European Parliament Policy Department for Economics, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies	Digital euro CBDC
34	The Digitalization of Money	Brunnermeier et al	2019	National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper	Future of digital money
35	The Economics of Fintech and Digital Currencies	Fatas et al	2019	CEPR Press	Digital currencies
36	Money and Payments: The U.S. Dollar in the Age of Digital Transformation	Federal Reserve System	2022	Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System	USD & Digital currencies
37	Fintech: The Experience so Far	International Monetary Fund	2019	IMF Policy Papers	Global fintech developments
38	Virtual Currencies – Monetary Dialogue July 2018	Kiel Institute for the World Economy	2018	European Parliament	Technological aspect of digital currencies

39	Kalifa Review of UK Fintech	Kalifa	2021	HM Treasury	UK Fintech & digital currencies
40	The Future of Payments	Patel et al	2020	Digital Monetary Institute	Innovation in payment sector
Blockchain and DLT					
41	Comparative Analysis of Blockchain Consensus Algorithms	Bach et al	2018	IEEE Conference	Blockchain
42	AI and Blockchain: A Disruptive Integration	Dinh & Thai	2018	Computer	Blockchain
43	Trade-Offs between Distributed Ledger Technology Characteristics	Kannengießler et al	2020	ACM Computing Surveys	DLT & blockchain
44	Analysis of the Possibilities for Improvement of BlockChain Technology	Mechkaroska et al	2018	IEEE 2018 26th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR)	Blockchain
45	Regulatory Approaches to the Tokenisation of Assets	OECD	2021	OECD Blockchain Policy Series	Regulation
46	Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and Blockchain	World Bank Group	2017	International Bank for Reconstruction and Development FinTech Note	DLT & Blockchain
CBDC from a global perspective					
47	Fintech, Cryptocurrencies, and CBDC: Financial Structural Transformation in China	Allen et al	2022	Journal of International Money and Finance	China's FinTech experience
48	Central Bank Digital Currencies: Foundational Principles and Core Features	Bank for International Settlements et al	2020	BIS Report	Design
49	Ready, Steady, Go? Results of the Third BIS Survey on Central Bank Digital Currency	Boar & Wehri	2021	BIS Papers	Central banks' global interest in CBDCs
50	Gaining Momentum - Results of the 2021 BIS Survey on Central Bank Digital Currencies	Kosse & Mattei	2022	BIS Papers	Central banks' global interest in CBDCs
51	Behind the Scenes of Central Bank Digital Currency: Emerging Trends, Insights, and Policy Lessons	Soderberg et al	2022	IMF Fintech Notes	Study of global advanced CBDC projects
Cryptocurrencies					
52	Bitcoin's Dirty Little Secrets	Blanch et al	2021	BofA Global Research	Bitcoin
53	Developing Central Bank Digital Currencies: A Reality Check during Cryptocurrency Euphoria	Cioroianu et al	2022		CBDC competing with cryptocurrencies
54	Why Would We Use Crypto Euros? Central Bank-Issued Cash – a User Perspective	Deutsche Bank	2021	Deutsche Bank Research 'EU Monitor'	CBDC interacting with cryptocurrencies
55	Bitcoin and Beyond: a Technical Survey on Decentralized Digital Currencies	Tschorsch & Scheuermann	2015	Humboldt University of Berlin	Overview of cryptocurrencies